

“Creating an Ambitious Open Science Action Plan within a European University Alliance” : 4EU+ use case

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4EU+ Alliance

8 universities working together

4EU+ Alliance is a European alliance of universities. The initial group consists of 6 universities located in France, Germany, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland and Denmark, that began working together in 2017. In 2019, 4EU+ was a winner of the Erasmus + “European Universities” call. So the Alliance was selected to be part of the European University pilot projects. The University of Geneva then Paris II Panthéon-Assas only joined the alliance in 2022, bringing it to 8 members.

Funding and projects

The Alliance was a winner of the **Erasmus + call** in 2019 and was awarded with €15 million in funding. 4EU+ recently received additional funding (€2 millions) from **Horizon 2020 "Science with and for society" call**. These two funds have enabled the development of projects: EUP/OneCore and TRAIN4EU+.

- **EUP / OneCore** (OneCore is a continuation of the past EUP project) : the aim is to work on the constitution of a common and interdisciplinary educational offer and to develop new services and common digital infrastructures.
- **TRAIN4EU** aims to improve the quality of R&I support at the 4EU+ member universities by developing a culture of co-learning, co-innovation and collaboration.

Open Science is a core value of those projects and Sorbonne University Library is mainly involved in two workpackages.

Table 1. Description of open science projects in which the Sorbonne University library is involved

Project	Work Package	Coordinator	Achievement
EUP (2019-2022) / OneCore (2022-2026)	WP4.2. Mainstream Open Science in 4EU+ universities	Sorbonne University	Training sessions on Open Science : “Open for you ! An introduction series to open science” : 2021-2022 cycle and 2022-2023 cycle
OneCore (2022-2026)	WP4.3. 4EU+ University Press -	University of Milan	Work still in progress (new project)
TRAIN4EU (2021-2023)	WP5. Development of recommendations for support centres / libraries in Open Science	University of Warsaw	Focus on WP5.3. : Reports and recommendations on : - Responsible publishing - Citizen sciences - Research data, management & FAIR data

Open science deliverables

Training sessions on Open Science: “Open for you! An introduction series to open science” (WP. 4.2)

The objective of the project is to increase researchers’ open science practices. The response to this objective has been to develop training in open science since the academic year 2021-2022. The main target public was PhD students within the 4EU+ Alliance, but our audience has grown steadily and we are now reaching PhD students, academic staff and researchers from outside the alliance.

Table 2. List of "Open for you!" webinars

Cycle 2021-2022	Cycle 2022-2023
What is Open Science?	Introduction to Open Science and Research Integrity
Cycle of scientific publication: an overview	Open Access and Open licences
What are my funders’ requirements on Open Science? A focus on Plan S	Publishing with the rights retention strategy: is it for me?
Strategies for publishing in Open Access journals	Preprint and Open Peer Review
Data Management Plans - one tool with many applications	Predatory publishers and identity fraud – how to identify dubious providers
Predatory publishers and identity fraud - how to identify dubious providers	Searching for open access works
Publication strategies for monographs in Humanities and Social Sciences	Managing FAIR Data in the Humanities: Approaches and Examples
Research Data Management - Introduction to FAIR and Open Data	The FAIR principles in science, technology and engineering – How to write a good Data Management Plan for FAIR research data
Open Research Software	Researcher ID and digital strategy: creating a real Orcid ID to be visible
Open science and the role of rights management	Open research software - how to disseminate it?
Humanities and FAIR data	
Citizen Science: producing data with people for innovating research	
Research Integrity and Open Science: Is sound science open science?	
Research Impact & Bibliometrics: open science, society, innovation	

How do we do it?

- The courses were each given by two trainers, from different universities wherever possible. We wanted to give an overview of the practices and tools available in each of our countries. That's why we felt it was important to cross points of view by involving two trainers from different countries.
- The recordings of the training sessions were sent to the participants and the materials were made available on Zenodo.
- In order to retain our audience, we have built different programmes for the 2021-2022 cycle and the 2023 cycle. Certain topics that form the basis of the training have been retained from one year to the other (Predatory publishers and identity fraud – how to identify dubious providers?). New subjects, more practical (Searching for open access works, Researcher ID and digital strategy: creating a real Orcid ID to be visible) or more disciplinary (FAIRData in HSS, FAIRData in science), have been added to the training programme.
- In order to make the webinars livelier, interviews of specialists and micro training with quiz were introduced for the second cycle. Interviewees for the training cycle included Johan Rooryck, Executive Director of cOAlition S and also researchers as ambassadors for open science such as Paola Masuzzo (Data Scientist and Independent Researcher) and Pierre Poulain (Paris-Cité University, Institut Jacques Monod), etc.

How does it work? These new formats have borne fruit, with the number of participants increasing year on year, averaging 168 per session (min: 89, max: 254) in 2023, compared with an average of 88 last year.

Focus on data training session

Training courses on FAIR and open data, as well as on DMP, have helped to improve mutual understanding of the institutional and national landscape relating to data, as well as the obligations of national funders.

Open Access Textbooks (WP. 4.3)

The objective of the project is to analyse the different practices about books production within our universities in order to define guidelines and to publish of one or two textbooks with the 4EU+ logo.

How do we do it?

1. Questionnaire: What are the University Presses process within our universities? What are the best practices?
2. Focus on textbooks: what is the literature review on textbook production experiences?
3. 4EU+ textbooks publication

How does it work? Work still in progress (new 4EU+ project)

Institutional practices and challenges analyse: publishing, citizen sciences, RDM and FAIR data (WP. 5.3)

The objective of the project is to analyse the different practices and challenges related to the Open Science agenda, and to make recommendations.

How do we do it?

1. The working group identified possible topics for study and decided to focus on 3 study topics:
 - Responsible publishing (open access university press, tools to measure the rate of OA publication filed in OA)
 - Citizen sciences
 - Research data, management & FAIR data
2. For these three study topics, they have identified weaknesses and strengths.
3. They have studied the national and institutional policies of the 4EU+ member institutions.
4. They drew a picture of the good and best practices within the 4EU+ alliance thanks to interviews.

Focus on the “Research data, management & FAIR data” part :

A 4-steps study :

- RDM services ecosystem in the 4EU+ universities
- RDM support activities and data stewardship
- RDM trainings
- RDM repositories

For each of these stages, a report was written describing the methodology, the limitations of the work, the conclusions and outlining a series of recommendations. The study was carried out using a benchmark of institutional websites, interviews and a workshop. It enabled us to gain a better understanding of the research data-related aspects within institutions and to produce common documents such as, for example, lists of skills according to the type of position, or a common training framework on a subject that is generally lacking in the training offered by institutions. A final report summarises these conclusions and the recommendations.

Recommendations - How the 4EU+ University Alliance can expand its collaboration and focus on RDM services?

- Strengthen collaboration between RDM services within the 4EU+
- Coordinate RDM services between local (unit, laboratory) and transversal (university) levels in each institution
- Support the development of new job profiles to address emerging RDM issues in the local context
- Implement data champion programs
- Develop joint RDM training courses within the 4EU+, such as a joint program or summer school
- Develop joint training courses on the ethical and legal aspects of RDM and on reproducibility
- Support the creation and maintenance of each partner's data repository
- Provide sustainable funding for long-term data preservation (beyond 10 years)
- Consider CoreTrustSeal (CTS) certification for all 4EU+ repositories.